

KINDS OF EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS OF THE BEST EVIDENCE RULE

Introduction

Evidence is the cornerstone of every system of law that strives to administer justice fairly. The courts must rely on material that is reliable and admissible. In India, the law of evidence is codified in the Indian Evidence Act (IEA), 1872,¹ a comprehensive statute, prepared by Sir James Fitzjames Stephen,² aimed to introduce certainty and uniformity in the rules of proof. Now, the IEA has been superseded by the Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam (BSA), 2023³ that brings clarity, especially in the context of electronic evidence.

Within this context, the types of evidence are critical. Also important is the doctrine of Best Evidence Rule, which requires that the most authentic and original form of evidence be produced. This research paper discusses the type of evidence recognised in Indian law and relevant case laws. It further examines the Best Evidence Rule in India, following it through from English common law, codification under the Act and the subsequent interpretation by Indian courts.

Concept and Definition of Evidence

The word *evidence* is derived from the Latin word *evidentia*, meaning “that which is obvious.”⁴ Section 3 of the IEA defines evidence to mean and include:⁵

1. All statements which the court permits or requires to be made before it by witnesses in relation to matters of fact under inquiry, commonly referred to as oral evidence; and
2. All documents including electronic records produced for the inspection of the court, which are termed as documentary evidence.

Under the BSA, 2023, the corresponding definition is found in Section 2(1)(e) which also clearly covers electronic record and digital formats.⁶ However, the term evidence does not

¹ Indian Evidence Act 1872

² JF Stephen, *The Indian Evidence Act: With an Introduction on the Principles of Judicial Evidence* (London, Macmillan 1872)

³ Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023

⁴ Oxford Latin Dictionary (Oxford University Press 2012) 676

⁵ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 3

⁶ Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023, s 2(1)(e)

include all that is produced in court; it refers only to that material which is admissible by law.⁷ This conceptual clarity provides the basis for a systematic classification of the types of evidence that have been recognised in Indian law.

Kinds of Evidence

1. Direct Evidence

Direct evidence establishes a fact in issue without any inference or presumption. Hence, it is the strongest type of evidence. For instance, an eyewitness to a crime is direct evidence. Section 60 of the IEA provides that oral evidence shall be direct,⁸ that is, it shall be perceived by the person through his own senses. The same is reaffirmed in Section 58 of BSA.⁹ However, courts are careful, because eyewitness testimony can be prone to error or bias. In *State of U.P. v. Krishna Gopal (1988)*,¹⁰ the Supreme Court noted that direct evidence of eyewitnesses is sufficient to establish guilt if it stands the test of cross-examination.

2. Indirect or Circumstantial Evidence

Circumstantial evidence does not directly prove the fact in issue, but is a series of circumstances from which the court can infer the existence of that fact. Section 3 of the IEA and Section 2 of BSA¹¹ acknowledges such evidence. Unlike direct evidence, it must use logical reasoning and connect the facts to form a conclusion. It is frequently used as the determining factor in criminal trials in which direct evidence is not available. The Supreme Court in *Hanumant Govind Nargundkar v. State of M.P. (1952)*¹² laid down that the chain of circumstances must be complete and must not leave any other hypothesis other than the guilt of the accused.

3. Primary Evidence

Primary evidence is the original document itself that is brought to the court for inspection. Section 62 of IEA defines primary evidence as the document itself, in its original form.¹³ It can now be found in Section 61 of the BSA,¹⁴ and is expanded to include electronic

⁷ Ratanlal and Dhirajlal, *The Law of Evidence* (27th edn, LexisNexis 2020) 12

⁸ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 60

⁹ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023*, s 58

¹⁰ *State of UP v Krishna Gopal* (1988) 4 SCC 302

¹¹ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023*, s 2

¹² *Hanumant Govind Nargundkar v State of M.P.* AIR 1952 SC 343

¹³ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 62

¹⁴ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023*, s 61

records as well. For example, the original sale deed is the primary evidence in a property dispute. The significance of primary evidence is associated with the "best evidence rule" that the best available source of evidence must be presented in front of the court. In the case of *J. Yashoda v. K. Shobha Rani (2007)*,¹⁵ the Court opined that primary evidence must be produced unless secondary evidence is admissible under the Act.

4. Secondary Evidence

Secondary evidence is an alternative to primary evidence and can be admissible only under the conditions laid down in Section 63 and 65 of the IEA.¹⁶ The relevant sections are Sections 62 and 64 of the BSA.¹⁷ It is important where primary documents are missing or destroyed and when they are with the other party. However, the onus of proof of why relying on secondary evidence is necessary falls on the party that wishes to rely on it. In *H. Siddiqui v. A. Ramalingam (2011)*,¹⁸ Supreme Court made it clear that secondary evidence can be admitted only if the non-production of primary evidence is justified under Section 65 of IEA.

5. Personal Evidence

Personal evidence occurs when a witness testifies to the facts he has personally witnessed. It is discussed in Sections 118-134 of the IEA,¹⁹ whereas BSA protects these principles under Sections 124-136.²⁰ It is considered reliable based on the credibility of the witness, his ability to correctly perceive events, and the extent to which his testimony is resilient to cross-examination. In *Vadivelu Thevar v. State of Madras (1957)*,²¹ the Supreme Court categorized oral evidence into three classes: wholly reliable, wholly unreliable and partly reliable, and emphasized the importance of corroboration in the case of partly reliable witnesses.

6. Real Evidence

Real or material evidence is physical evidence that is introduced into court to be examined, such as weapons, bloodstained clothing, or fingerprints. The BSA, like the IEA, implicitly acknowledges such evidence through provisions dealing with facts, inspection, and

¹⁵ *J. Yashoda v K. Shobha Rani* (2007) 5 SCC 730

¹⁶ Indian Evidence Act 1872, ss 63, 65

¹⁷ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, ss 62, 64

¹⁸ *H. Siddiqui v A. Ramalingam* (2011) 4 SCC 240

¹⁹ Indian Evidence Act 1872, ss 118–134

²⁰ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, ss 124–136

²¹ *Vadivelu Thevar v State of Madras* AIR 1957 SC 614

expert testimony. It needs proper chain of custody and forensic analysis. For instance, in a murder trial, a murder weapon with the accused's fingerprints on it is real evidence. In *Pulukuri Kottaya v. King Emperor (1947)*,²² recovery of a weapon based upon disclosure statement was considered important material/real evidence.

7. Judicial Evidence

Judicial evidence is received by the court during the trial and becomes part of the judicial record. This includes evidence offered on oath, documentary evidence tendered in court and facts judicially noticed under Section 57 of the IEA.²³ The BSA, through Sections 52-55,²⁴ still considers it as a category of evidence. For instance, certified copies of public documents, once admitted, constitute a part of the judicial evidence. In *Sat Paul v. Delhi Administration (1976)*,²⁵ where testimonial evidence in the court was found more trustworthy than extra-judicial statements in the past.

8. Extra-Judicial Evidence

Extra-judicial evidence is any evidence procured outside the courtroom which may then be presented before the court. For example, this includes confessions made to non-official individuals, or evidence obtained during a police investigation, but not yet tendered in judicial proceedings. In *State of Punjab v. Bhajan Singh (2011)*,²⁶ the Supreme Court noted that extra-judicial confessions, although weak evidence, may still be resorted to if they are voluntary, truthful and corroborated by other evidence. Courts, however, exercise great caution before convicting an accused based only on the extra-judicial evidence.

9. Oral Evidence

Oral evidence, as defined in Section 59 of the IEA,²⁷ means all evidence by witnesses given in court, except where documentary evidence is required by law. Section 60 also requires oral testimony to be direct at all times. Sections 57-58 of the BSA deal with oral evidence.²⁸ It is widely recognized that oral evidence is critical particularly to criminal trials where witness testimony is key. However, the courts are aware of the inherent limitations of oral evidence,

²² *Pulukuri Kottaya v King Emperor* AIR 1947 PC 67

²³ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 57

²⁴ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, ss 52–55

²⁵ *Sat Paul v Delhi Administration* (1976) 1 SCC 727

²⁶ *State of Punjab v Bhajan Singh* (2011) 7 SCC 421.

²⁷ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 59.

²⁸ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, ss 57–58.

such as human error, lapses in memory, or outright lies. In *State of Maharashtra v. Sukhdev Singh (1992)*,²⁹ oral evidence was taken to be reliable only when it was supported by material evidence.

10. Documentary Evidence

Documentary evidence means all the documents presented to the court for inspection under Section 3 of the Evidence Act. In the BSA, documentary evidence is defined in section 2(1)(d) and explicitly covers electronic records.³⁰ It is split into public documents and private documents. Examples are contracts, deeds, government paper, and letters. In *Kaliya v. State of Madhya Pradesh (2013)*,³¹ the Supreme Court ruled that documentary evidence has a greater evidentiary value than oral testimony, if both are available, as documents are less prone to human error.

11. Hearsay Evidence

Hearsay evidence is not directly perceived by the witness, but obtained from another person. Generally, it is not acceptable under Indian law. In *Subramaniam v. Public Prosecutor (1956)*,³² the Privy Council explained that hearsay evidence is inadmissible unless it is not relevant for the truth of its contents but to show that the statement was made. Indian courts have always held that the admission of hearsay would erode trust in the judicial process. Exceptions are available under sections 6, 32 and 33 of the IEA,³³ such as dying declarations and statements in the course of business. The BSA takes the same view in Sections 6, 26 and 27.³⁴

12. Electronic Evidence

Electronic or digital evidence has become prominent with the increasing use of technology. Section 65B of the IEA contains the framework for admissibility of electronic records and requires a certificate under Section 65B (4).³⁵ This is more fully addressed under the BSA in Section 63. Electronic evidence is essential today with emails, CCTV footage, call records and digital contracts all playing a key role in the outcome of many modern cases. In

²⁹ *State of Maharashtra v Sukhdev Singh* (1992) 3 SCC 700.

³⁰ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, s 2(1)(d).

³¹ *Kaliya v State of Madhya Pradesh* (2013) 10 SCC 758.

³² *Subramaniam v Public Prosecutor* [1956] 1 WLR 965 (PC)

³³ Indian Evidence Act 1872, ss 6, 32, 33

³⁴ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam* 2023, ss 6, 26, 27

³⁵ Indian Evidence Act 1872, s 65B (4)

Tomaso Bruno v. State of UP (2015),³⁶ Court encouraged the use of modern technology and failure to produce available electronic evidence can weaken the prosecution.

The Best Evidence Rule

The Best Evidence Rule is a cardinal rule of evidence law that demands that the best available evidence be brought before the court. The rule evolved from English common law,³⁷ and was intended to reduce the risk of fraud and misrepresentation by ensuring that courts are guided by the most accurate material. Its importance is not that secondary evidence is entirely excluded, but that secondary evidence is admissible only where primary evidence cannot be produced for reasons outside the control of the party.

In India, the rule is codified mainly in Sections 61 to 65 of the IEA.³⁸ Section 61 states that the contents of documents shall be proved either by primary or by secondary evidence. Section 62 defines primary evidence while Section 63 defines secondary evidence. Section 64 provides that documents have to be proved by primary evidence unless otherwise provided under the Act. Section 65 lists the circumstances in which secondary evidence can be produced. In the BSA, these are now found in Sections 60 to 64.³⁹

In *Anvar P.V. v. P.K. Basheer (2014)*,⁴⁰ the court ruled that electronic records can only be admissible if the conditions of Section 65B of IEA are met (certificate requirement). This case extended the Best Evidence Rule to electronic records by requiring a certification. In *Arjun Panditrao Khotkar v. Kailash Kushanrao Gorantyal (2020)*,⁴¹ court reaffirmed the *Anvar P.V.* case and made the Section 65B certificate compulsory. The BSA codifies these judicially developed standards in statutory form by specifically codifying the admissibility of electronic records in Section 63.

Critical Analysis

The Best Evidence Rule, although foundational, is not without criticism. One of its strongest criticisms is its inflexibility, particularly with regard to documentary and electronic evidence. The rigid insistence that only primary evidence can be produced has resulted in the

³⁶ *Tomaso Bruno v State of UP (2015)* 7 SCC 178

³⁷ James Bradley Thayer, *A Preliminary Treatise on Evidence at the Common Law* (Boston, Little, Brown & Co 1898) 390

³⁸ Indian Evidence Act 1872, ss 61–65

³⁹ *Bhartiya Sakshya Adhiniyam 2023*, ss 60–64

⁴⁰ *Anvar P.V. v P.K. Basheer (2014)* 10 SCC 473

⁴¹ *Arjun Panditrao Khotkar v Kailash Kushanrao Gorantyal (2020)* 7 SCC 1

unjust exclusion of otherwise reliable material. This is especially true in the use of Section 65B of the IEA which rendered electronic records admissible only if accompanied by a certificate of authenticity. Section 63 of BSA, 2023, persists with this approach, mandating certification for electronic evidence. While this assures authenticity, it can also limit access to important digital data when the party is unable to obtain certification.

Another limitation of the rule is that it often presumes that the original version of evidence is necessarily more reliable. However, contemporary technology shows that copies, digitalizations, and certified reproductions can be as good as the originals.⁴² The strict reliance on "best" evidence has in some cases delayed trials, invited hyper-technical objections, and imposed undue burden on parties. Nevertheless, the core logic of the rule - that courts must use the most trustworthy form of evidence - is sound. Without this rule, counterfeit or altered copies would easily circulate and be used in Court. The challenge is balancing the authenticity called for by the rule with the flexibility of a digital age.⁴³

Conclusion

Evidence is the lifeblood of adjudication and the law governing it must constantly change to meet new realities. IEA's classification and regulation of the types of evidence offers a robust framework that has lasted the test of time. Now, BSA, 2023 continues its fundamental principles, updating the law to adapt to technological and social developments. Within this framework, the Best Evidence Rule ensures that courts make their decisions on the basis of the most authentic material available, thus improving the reliability of their decisions.

Still, the rule needs careful reinterpretation in the age of digitalisation. Too much flexibility can ruin reliability, and excessive rigidity can rule out real evidence. The Supreme Court jurisprudence shows a continuing struggle to find this balance. Ultimately, the law of evidence is not a static thing. It must adapt to the changes in society, technology, and the general quest for justice. Despite its strong roots in tradition, the Best Evidence Rule is still valid today as long as it is applied with a spirit of pragmatism and fairness.

⁴² Shweta Vashisht, 'Revisiting the Best Evidence Rule in the Digital Era' (2021) 7(2) *NLUJ Law Review* 89, 97

⁴³ Avtar Singh, *Principles of the Law of Evidence* (22nd edn, Central Law Publications 2018) 144